

APPENDIX I

Activity details

I.1 Objective

The objective of the activity is that students should form constellations (Form A) or molecules (Form B), which meet the exact pattern of stars or atoms that are presented to them as targets of each level. For this, students should work in teams in which each participant will have to select, among a set of stars or atoms, the quantity and color of elements indicated. In addition, they should consider that there are multiple solutions and that communicating is the way to take agreement.

I.2 Narrative

In Form A of the instrument, test taker is introduced to an astronaut, who invites he or she to help him get to his destination (Figure I.1).

Figure I.1: Activity introduction Forma A

Then, as the first level begins, the ship's co-crew, Alpha and Beta, discuss with test taker the objectives of finding constellations, and talk about the buttons on the interface (Figure I.2).

Figure I.2: Activity main view Forma A

At the end of each level, results are presented to the test taker with the achievement or not of the actions they carried out (Figure I.3).

Figure I.3: End of a level Forma A

On the other hand, in Form B, test taker is introduced to a scientist, who invites he or she to help her in the laboratory (Figure I.4).

Figure I.4: Activity introduction Forma B

Then, at the beginning of the first level, the laboratory colleagues, Neutron and Proton, talk with test taker about the objectives of finding molecules, and talk about the buttons on the interface (Figure I.5).

Figure I.5: Activity main view Forma B

At the end of each level, results are presented to the test taker with the achievement or not of the actions they carried out (Figure I.6).

Figure I.6: End of a level Forma B

I.3 Levels target

Form A

Figure I.7: Constellation target in each level of Forma A

Form B

Figure I.8: Molecule target in each level of Form B